

What constitutes success in mathematics education in Ireland and what obstacles stand in the way of this success: A decade in review

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Abstract

Success in mathematics means many different things to many different people. In Ireland, from a policy perspective, the notion of what it means for students to be successful in mathematics at post-primary level has changed in recent years. This change in perspective coincides with the implementation of mathematics curriculum reform and incentives to increase the uptake of study of advanced mathematics. This paper focuses on the evolution of the notion of success in mathematics education over the past decade and the role of different initiatives, which impacted, in different ways, teachers' and students' perceptions of success. Drawing on various research findings, the paper identifies the challenges – teacher knowledge, mathematics instructional time and students' attitudes and motivations – brought about by the initiatives which have limited access to 'success' for many students. Finally, the author will discuss that while the shift in what constitutes success was admirable it has had some many unforeseen consequences. It is these consequences that will need to be considered by all involved in mathematics education in future re-conceptualisations of success at post-primary level in Ireland.

Keywords: Project Maths, Bonus Points, teacher knowledge, time, student motivation

Introduction

Since 2012 the post-primary mathematics education landscape in Ireland has changed dramatically and with these changes came a change in what many perceive constitutes success in mathematics education. In this paper, I will discuss the initiatives that have brought about significant change to mathematics education in Ireland over the past decade, analyse their impact on stakeholders' perceptions of success in mathematics at post-primary level, and investigate the (unforeseen) challenges that have affected the uniform adoption of the perception of success espoused by Government agencies and policy makers. The identification of these challenges has been the kernel of much of my own research in this time period.

2010 and the Introduction of Project Maths

In 2010, a revised mathematics curriculum, which had been piloted across 24 schools between 2008 and 2010, was rolled out across all post-primary schools in Ireland. This reform movement was initiated for two reasons. Firstly, according to Byrne et al. (2021), at the turn of the new millennium there was mounting evidence to suggest that the mathematics curriculum at the time was not serving the needs of the Irish people and was not producing graduates from the post-primary system equipped with the knowledge and skills needed for a knowledge economy. Many believed that this deficiency in students' mathematical capabilities stemmed from an over-reliance on rote learning in Irish mathematics classroom (Lyons et al., 2003) and the declining attitudes towards mathematics among post-primary

school students (NCCA, 2005). Secondly, there was a need for better alignment between the primary and post-primary curricula in Ireland. In 1999, the primary school mathematics curriculum was reformed while the previous full-scale reform at post-primary level was conducted in the 1970s¹. As such, the alignment between the two curricula was tenuous at best, and a reform to the post-primary mathematics curriculum at both Junior and Senior Cycle was necessary to modernise a dated mathematics curriculum and to improve the alignment between the two curricula. These two shortcomings led to the introduction of the revised curriculum, known locally as *Project Maths*.

Project Maths was inspired by the Realistic Mathematics Education [RME] movement as this was seen as the “*most fashionable approach among mathematics educators*” at the time (NCCA, 2005, p.6). However, learning from the mistakes of previous curriculum reform efforts, those responsible for the design of this new curriculum were cautious not to overly depend on one single ideological standpoint, and so instead were inspired by appropriate aspects of the RME movement while at the same time ensuring that the new curriculum was aligned with international best practice and the needs of the Irish economy (O’Meara & Milinkovic, 2023). This approach led to the implementation of a curriculum which sought to “*teach mathematics in a way which promotes real understanding, where students can appreciate the relevance of what they are learning and its application to everyday life...*” (Project Maths Implementation Support Group [PMISG], 2010, p.12).

Project Maths advocated for a fundamental shift in the approach to mathematics teaching, learning and assessment (Cosgrove et al., 2012). As such, the notion of what it meant to be successful in mathematics changed. Success, as elicited by the reformed curriculum, was achieved through students developing and demonstrating conceptual understanding of a topic and being able to use mathematics to solve authentic problems (PMISG, 2010). Central to achieving this success was the role of students in the construction of their own knowledge, which was a shift from the procedural, top-down, approach to teaching favoured in the past (Lyons et al., 2003). Finally, successful mathematics teaching and learning resulted in students viewing the subject as an interconnected body of knowledge rather than a collection of isolated ideas. This revised understanding of success in mathematics was fundamentally different to what had been promoted previously and highlighted the lofty ambitions of this curriculum reform. However, the realisation of this perception of success encountered many challenges.

Challenges facing Implementation of Project Maths

Teacher Knowledge

The success of any reform movement depends on the teachers who are required to interpret and enact it (Spillane, 1999). With such significant changes to the teaching and learning of mathematics the demands placed on teachers changed, in particular in relation to

¹ In the 1970s the curriculum at both Junior and Senior Cycle was reformed, similar to the reform implemented most recently. In 1987 an updated curriculum was introduced at lower secondary level but this did not involve major reform nor was the focus on improving the alignment with the primary school curriculum (Oldham, 2007). Subsequently to ensure the mathematics curricula at upper and lower secondary school were aligned the curriculum at upper secondary school was then updated separately in 1992

the knowledge they needed in order to teach effectively. Project Maths aimed to secure a change in teaching approaches and practices and as Putnam et al. (1992) suggest such change also requires a change in a teacher's knowledge base. In order for students to develop conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills, as espoused by the new curriculum, teachers had to expand their own knowledge base to ensure they were in a position to help students achieve this success. While Shulman (1986) proposed three domains of knowledge for effective teaching, namely subject matter content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and curricular knowledge, many researchers, such as Ball et al. (2008), spoke of the need for models of teacher knowledge to be continuously refined and updated in line with changes in mathematics curricula and teaching approaches. As such, the changes brought about by Project Maths also brought about the need for different knowledge domains among teachers. It was these different knowledge domains that I identified in my own PhD study via a model labelled the *Ladder of Knowledge* (see Figure 1). This model, which built on the work of Shulman (1986) and Ball et al. (2008), outlined the three knowledge domains necessary to teach the revised curriculum effectively (subject matter knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and knowledge for effective teaching) and also provided sub-domains which allowed teachers to transition between these key knowledge domains (knowledge of real life applications, knowledge of connections, historical knowledge, knowledge of school maths and transforming knowledge) (O'Meara, 2011).

Figure 1. Ladder of Knowledge

While the provision of a model of teacher knowledge helped to identify the knowledge domains needed to facilitate student success and the effective teaching of mathematics, further research, indicated that work was still needed to help teachers to develop the different types of knowledge outlined in the model. The work of O'Meara (2011) showed that in-service teachers felt confident in only one domain, subject matter knowledge, and deficient in all others. This was also apparent when their knowledge was assessed, with issues identified across many of the domains, including knowledge of applications, knowledge of connections, historical knowledge and transforming knowledge (O'Meara, 2011). Subsequent studies have reported similar findings; for example, O'Meara et al., (2020a) found post-primary teachers

did not possess sufficient knowledge of connections and knowledge of school mathematics, primarily due to unfamiliarity with the mathematical content and pedagogical approaches employed at the upper end of primary school. Consequently, post-primary teachers lacking this knowledge could not align their pedagogical approaches with those experienced by students in earlier years of schooling. Studies have also found that Irish pre-service teachers do not possess the required knowledge in many other domains included in the Ladder of Knowledge; for example, O'Meara and Fitzmaurice's (2022) study illustrated pre-service teachers', in the penultimate year of their teacher education programme, demonstrated superficial understanding of the applicability of mathematics. Less than 12% of the sample in this study were able to provide an accurate, uncontrived real-life scenario that would require one to perform subtraction or multiplication of rational numbers, while no pre-service teachers could provide such a scenario for the operation of division. These studies indicate that teachers, at both in-service and pre-service level, do not possess the requisite knowledge to facilitate students to succeed in the new curriculum. It must be acknowledged, however, that this is through no fault of their own, given that teachers have not been given sufficient opportunities to develop the array of knowledge types proposed in the Ladder of Knowledge. This shortfall in learning opportunities for teachers has been identified in a number of studies (O'Meara, Johnson & Leavy, 2020; Fitzmaurice, O'Meara & Johnson, 2021), and until such opportunities are provided to teachers, mathematical success for Irish students – as described by Project Maths – will be extremely difficult to achieve.

Instructional Time

A second challenge which has the potential to limit the success experienced by *all* students in mathematics relates to the time available to implement the curriculum. Carroll (1989) described how academic success is dependent on variables representing the amount of time available to learn, the time needed to learn, and the time a student is willing to spend learning. More recently, a large body of literature has demonstrated strong, positive correlations between instruction time and student achievement (Benavot & Amadi, 2004). In the Irish context, a study by O'Meara and Prendergast (2017) found that 89% of Junior Cycle teachers and 92% of Senior Cycle teachers believed that Project Maths, and its new conceptualisation of success, had impacted on the time required to teach the curriculum. However, the majority of these teachers (88% at Junior Cycle and 79% at Senior Cycle) reported that the time allocated to mathematics had not changed with the introduction of the new curriculum. As a result, 62% of the teachers ($n = 316$) strongly disagreed or disagreed that there was sufficient time available to achieve the goals of Project Maths at Junior Cycle, while the corresponding figure for Senior Cycle was 82%. Furthermore, this study uncovered significant variations in the time available to deliver the curriculum, with the allocated instruction time ranging from 120 to 300 minutes per week (pw) in first year; from 145 to 240 minutes pw in second year; from 145 to 249 minutes pw in third year; from 175 to 290 minutes pw in fifth year and from 180 to 290 minutes pw in sixth year. These variations coupled with the provision of voluntary, additional lessons outside of the school day by some, but not all, teachers meant that students, even in the same school, can receive varying amounts of instruction time. These students, regardless of the school they attend or the teacher

they are assigned, are studying the same syllabi and preparing for the same examination with the same success criteria yet receiving various amounts of instruction time (Prendergast & O'Meara, 2017). Thus, until students are provided with equitable access to mathematics instruction, success for some will continue to be much more accessible than it is for others solely based on the school they attend or the teacher they are assigned.

The Bonus Points Initiative

In 2012 another significant change to mathematics education at post-primary level occurred with the introduction of the *Bonus Points Initiative* [BPI]. In Ireland, mathematics is not a compulsory subject at upper post-primary level; however, due in part to the matriculation requirements of Irish Higher Education Institutes, virtually all Irish students study mathematics at Senior Cycle. For example, in June 2022, 58,056 students sat the Leaving Certificate (the terminal Senior Cycle assessment) and 57,248 (98.61%) of these students sat a mathematics examination. While students do not generally have a choice about studying mathematics at upper post-primary school, they do have agency regarding the level they study. There are currently three levels of mathematics available to students: Higher Level; Ordinary Level; and Foundation Level. Higher Level is the most advanced form of mathematics that students can study. Ordinary Level covers many of the same concepts addressed at Higher Level, but not to the same depth. Foundation Level is a separate course of study centred on basic mathematical skills.

Researchers ascertain that the study of advanced mathematics (Higher Level in Ireland) facilitates the development of a variety of skills, such as decision making and critical thinking, that underpin a scientifically literate workforce, determine future academic success at third level and future income (Wolf, 2002; Chinnappan et al., 2008; Kennedy et al., 2014; Hine et al., 2015). Despite the importance of mathematics and the necessity for a mathematically literate workforce for economic growth and personal advancement, many countries worldwide, including Ireland, report low numbers of students studying advanced mathematics at upper post-primary level. Prior to 2012, the proportion of students studying Higher Level mathematics at upper post-primary level in Ireland was extremely low when compared to other school subjects. For example, for the 2011 Leaving Certificate, 15.8% of students opted for the Higher Level paper, with the corresponding figures for English and Irish being 63.7% and 32.3%, respectively. In 2012, policy makers in Ireland recognised the value of increasing this proportion due to the aforementioned benefits and so introduced the BPI. The BPI had two objectives: first, to increase the number of students opting for Higher Level mathematics; and second, to improve students' mathematical competency. In order to achieve these goals, the BPI incentivised students' 'successful' completion of the Higher Level mathematics course at upper post-primary level, and by consequence, assigned Higher Level mathematics a unique status.

In Ireland, students are accepted onto third-level courses based on a points system that equates students' performance in a subject-area for the Leaving Certificate with a point score. Undertaking a subject at Higher Level yields a greater number of points; for instance, the top grade in Higher Level, H1, is valued at 100 points, while the top grade for Ordinary Level, O1, merits 56 points. The student's total points from their six best subject is then used as the

determining factor for their entry into third level, thus rendering the Leaving Certificate a gatekeeper to tertiary education. The BPI is situated in the context of this competitive ‘points race’ for third-level entry. The BPI awards students who achieve a passing grade (>40%) in Higher Level mathematics an additional 25 points. Consequently, a H4 grade (60%-69%) in mathematics is now valued at 91 points (66 + 25), while the same grade in any other subject yields 66 points. The BPI achieved one of its goals in that the proportion of students undertaking Higher Level mathematics has increased from 15.8% in 2011 to 37.1% in 2022; however, it has also had a significant impact on how students, parents and teachers now perceive success in mathematics. For many, success now means “enduring” Higher Level mathematics in the hope of “doing enough” to obtain 40% to secure the coveted additional 25 points, thus increasing their likelihood of securing a college place. This new perception of success has presented numerous challenges for students and teachers alike.

Challenges Associated with the BPI

Student Profile

The first challenge presented by the BPI relates to the new student profile in Higher Level mathematics classes. In a study conducted by Treacy et al. (2020), a large proportion of teachers (61.5%) voiced concerns regarding the BPI. For these teachers, the BPI has resulted in the need to provide greater support to “weaker” students and cater for “mixed ability” cohorts to a much greater extent than was previously the case, primarily due to “unsuitable” candidates now persisting with HL mathematics. According to Linchevski and Kutscher (1998), mathematics is one of the more difficult subjects for working with mixed ability groupings, while Hallam and Ireson (2003) suggested that such grouping is inappropriate for mathematics. The BPI was introduced without any apparent consideration for the impact that it may have on class profiles and as such, teachers received no training in dealing with the knock-on effects of the BPI, including guidance on how to develop teaching strategies to cater for more mixed ability classes.

(Extrinsic) Student Motivation

A second challenge that has affected the successful implementation of the BPI relates to students’ motivations for studying Higher Level mathematics. The findings from a study conducted by O’Meara et al. (2023) show that students are now predominantly extrinsically, as opposed to intrinsically, motivated to study Higher Level mathematics. For example, 46.2% of the 911 Higher Level students surveyed indicated that the BPI was the most influential reason behind their decision to pursue Higher Level mathematics, while a further 7.2% of students cited that the CAO points on offer for Higher Level mathematics was the determining factor. This is a cause for concern as research has shown that extrinsic motivators, such as the BPI, do not work over time (Adamma, Ekwutosim & Unamba, 2018). In fact, the presence of extrinsic motivational factors can lead to diminished intrinsic motivation among students (Biehler & Snowman, 1990). Therefore, the role that the BPI is currently playing in motivating students to study Higher Level mathematics may have negative effects on students’ affective reaction to the subject.

These challenges have meant that only one of the goals of the BPI has been successfully achieved. While the number of students studying Higher Level mathematics has increased, only 18.9% of teachers in the Treacy et al. (2020) study believe that the BPI has resulted in an overall improvement in students' mathematical ability. This assertion is supported when one compares students' results in the Leaving Certificate mathematics examination before and after the introduction of the BPI (Treacy et al., 2020). The challenges facing the BPI discussed here offer some insights into the potential reasons why the BPI has failed in its mission to improve the mathematical skills and understanding of post-primary students. The new notion of success associated with the BPI involves "hanging on at higher level to gain bonus points" (Treacy et al, 2020, p.1433), meaning that the BPI could be having an unintended negative impact on students' mathematical ability. Furthermore, fears now exist that if the bonus points are removed completely, as has been advocated by some teachers, Ireland may see a lower proportion of students opt for Higher Level mathematics than was the case when the Irish Government first set about rectifying this issue in 2012 (O'Meara et al., 2023).

Conclusion

The concept of what it means to be successful in mathematics has changed in Ireland as the curriculum has evolved and new initiatives have been introduced. Consequently, over the past decade, success in mathematics has been perceived in various, and in some cases, unintended ways by policymakers, teachers, parents and students in Ireland. The Project Maths curriculum espouses a view of success as students seeing and experiencing mathematics as an interconnected body of knowledge, and becoming adept problem solvers who recognise the prevalence of mathematics in the world around them. For students, mathematics has a unique status, offering additional, valuable points as part of the points race for third-level entry. In many cases, this has led to the need to *endure* in mathematics, with success equated to achieving a pass grade to secure the bonus points, often to the detriment of their disposition towards the subject. Many teachers believe that the success espoused by Project Maths is almost unattainable given the lack of support they have received for developing the requisite knowledge to teach in this way, the failure to recognise the greater time demands of teaching in such a manner, and the heightened demands of teaching larger cohorts with broader ranges of ability which has stemmed from the simultaneous introduction of the BPI. Thus, even if educational changes, such as Project Maths and the BPI, serve to promote a particular perspective of success, this may not be how it is received by others. Such initiatives may lead to unintended perceptions of success and potentially, inadvertently, adversely impact the very issues they set out to address. It follows then that any future initiative which may impact on how success in mathematics is perceived should be carefully configured, taking into account any potential, unintended consequences.

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